

Policy Insight Briefing

Executive Summary

This brief from the GREAT project, provides policy recommendations drawing on contributions from policymakers, academics, game developers, UN agencies, investors, and civil society organisations at a recent workshop held in New York. The paper outlines how games function as a powerful infrastructure for policy dialogue, citizen engagement and voice, climate action, and systemic change.

Introduction

The GREAT (Games Realising Effective & Affective Transformation) Project explores the potential of games to foster social engagement and enhance dialogue between citizens and policymakers. A programme of practical case studies is underway, fostering citizen engagement and in the democratic process, with a focus on climate change policy priorities. Games culture is ubiquitous, and games are now this preeminent entertainment media globally, but their potential for interaction between citizens and policymakers has not yet been explored. The GREAT case studies leverage innovative engagement strategies to investigate how games-based activities can enable citizens to express their views on social and policy dilemmas. This initiative is supported by UK Research and Innovation and the EU's Horizon Europe program..

Methods

GREAT deploys technologies and methodologies that create new communication channels between citizens and policymakers, generating actionable insights for policy makers while respecting ethics and data privacy. This is achieved through co-designed, scalable interventions tested in real-world conditions, engaging audiences that can be difficult to reach using more established methodologies. Two principal approaches are investigated: Firstly, dilemma-based serious games are used to generate in-depth qualitative insights from a relatively small, moderated group of participants. Secondly, questions for players are embedded in high profile games, enabling quantitative data to be obtained from very large numbers of respondents, who can be engaged at global, national or district level. Throughout the project, we employ participatory methods, involving key audiences, including policy stakeholders, in the design, prototyping, and research phases. Authentic input, interaction, and collaboration are crucial, with continuous feedback and optimization. With our citizen science approach, we go beyond mere consultation, uncovering implicit knowledge through varying degrees of participation, from consultation to empowerment. While the focus of GREAT is on the global challenges of sustainability and climate change the project methodologies are both scalable and transferable to other issues.

Games can function as:

- A bridge between citizens and institutions at a time of declining trust in traditional political processes.
- A parallel public sphere where dialogue can occur across geopolitical boundaries.
- A scalable engagement mechanism capable of reaching millions of players in ways that conventional consultations cannot.
- Effectively facilitate a two-way dialogue, listening to players, understanding sentiment to produce actionable insights.

Games and Policy Dialogue: From Voice to Impact

Giving Players a Voice

A central theme was the demonstrated willingness of players to engage with societal issues when approached respectfully and non-intrusively. Experiences discussed during the workshop indicated:

- Short, well-integrated in-game prompts can achieve high engagement and completion rates.
- Players respond positively when participation is framed as having a voice as opposed to being 'taught' or 'persuaded'.
- Large-scale engagement can generate globally comparable data on attitudes toward climate, sustainability, and governance.

The Policy Challenge: What Happens After Data Collection?

While data collection at scale is achievable, participants highlighted a gap between citizen input and policy outcomes. Key challenges identified include:

- Policy focus: Define a clearly articulated policy objective before engaging players at scale
- Translation: Policymakers may lack the data literacy or frameworks needed to interpret player-generated insights.
- Feedback loops: Players rarely see how their input influences decisions, weakening long-term trust and engagement.

Toward Actionable Policy Pathways

The workshop identified pathways to strengthen the link between games and policy impact:

- Align game-based consultations with formal policy mechanisms (e.g. parliamentary petitions, national consultations).
- Partner with policy intermediaries who understand legislative and regulatory processes.
- Use smaller, facilitated dilemma-based games to define priorities, followed by large-scale in-game engagement.
- Treating policy engagement as an iterative dialogue rather than consultation.

In-Game Activations: Awareness, Behaviour, and Hope

Design for Engagement, Not Overload

Participants emphasised that climate-related content must be carefully designed to avoid fatigue or disengagement, particularly among younger audiences. Effective approaches should:

- Integrate sustainability into existing mechanics (intrinsic) rather than adding external (extrinsic) messaging.
- Use accessible language (e.g. “nature” rather than politicised terminology).
- Offer agency and choice over prescriptive instruction.
- Be conscious of potential survey fatigue amongst players

Behaviour Change and Real-World Action

Evidence shared during the workshop indicated:

- In-game experiences can prompt real-world actions when players feel empowered rather than judged.
- Collective events and time-bound activations can amplify impact.
- Players often want to do more but lack clear guidance on what actions matter.

Games can act as navigational tools, helping players move from concern to action.

Extended Realities (XR), Empathy, and the Next Frontier

Extended reality (XR) technologies were highlighted as a powerful next step, specifically:

- Build empathy through embodied experience.
- Make global or abstract issues feel personal.
- Support measurable shifts in perception and understanding.

XR was framed not as a replacement for games, but as a complementary medium that expands the engagement toolkit.

Cross-Cutting Themes and Key Insights

The workshop identified several unifying themes:

- Dialogue over didacticism: Listening is as important as informing.
- Focus and clarity: Impact requires targeted policy goals and clear success metrics.
- Hope and agency: Especially for younger audiences, solutions must accompany problems.
- Collaboration: Meaningful change depends on partnerships across industry, academia, policy, and civil society.
- Scalability with care: Large reach must be balanced with respect for player experience and not disrupt player 'flow'.

Insights for policy dialogue

Games are emerging as authentic critical infrastructures for engagement, dialogue, and transformation. The challenge ahead is how intentionally and collaboratively this potential is realised. In aligning player voice, industry innovation, and policy priorities, the GREAT project and its partners can help turn play into participation, data into dialogue, and engagement into impact.

Summary Recommendations

- **1. Define policy objectives early** and co-design game-based interventions with policymakers.
- **2. Embed player voice mechanisms** directly into games in non-intrusive, time-efficient ways.
- **3. Develop feedback loops** that show participants how their input influences outcomes.
- **4. Prioritise systems-level decarbonisation**, focusing on efficiency gains with co-benefits.
- **5. Invest in creative integration**, ensuring sustainability content aligns with gameplay and player motivation.
- **6. Support research and measurement**, including longitudinal studies of behaviour and attitude change.
- **7. Frame sustainability with hope**, highlighting achievable actions and collective progress.

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Further information

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